

Hollow Fibre Membrane Contactors for CO₂ Capture

Edoardo Panziera^{1, *}, Lois Sandra Sai-Obodai¹, Yusif Rhule Sam¹, Esther Praise Avor¹, Amir Ghobadi¹

¹Ionada Inc, Canada.

*Corresponding author. Email address: admin@ionada.com

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Amir Ghobadi:

Esther Praise Avor:

Yusif Rhule Sam:

Lois Sandra Sai-Obodai:

Edoardo Panziera

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors have no conflict of interest relevant to this article.

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Abstract

Hollow fiber membrane contactors have emerged as an attractive and promising technology for post-combustion carbon dioxide (CO₂) capture by contacting exhaust gas with amines. This study focuses on investigating the performance of a modularized PTFE hollow fiber membrane contactor developed by Ionada. Comparative analyses were conducted between Ionada's technology and a traditional packed bed column. Results from simulations indicate a remarkable 20% reduction in solvent regeneration requirement and a 28% decrease in amine losses when employing Ionada's contactor, while maintaining the same operating conditions and target CO₂ removal as the packed bed column. Consequently, these findings translate into substantial operational cost savings for carbon capture processes. The simulation results were validated through experimental runs, revealing an average absolute deviation of only 4% when comparing CO₂ mass flux. Furthermore, the technology exhibits scalability, as an increase in the number of modules allows for the treatment of flue gas streams with higher flowrates without necessitating a complete unit change. Notably, scaling up the system correspondingly enhances absorption efficiency.

Keywords

Hollow fibre membrane contactors; CO₂ capture; CO₂ mass flux; CO₂ loading; modelling and simulation; polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE).

1. Introduction

With the adverse effect of global warming on the environment and human health, the need to take action towards curbing greenhouse gas emissions into the atmosphere has been very critical to the sustenance of life. The most predominant greenhouse gas in the atmosphere is CO₂, and this is mainly due to our over-dependence on fossil fuel source of energy, namely coal, crude oil and natural gas. Among the various proposals made to minimize CO₂ emissions and mitigate the harsh effects of global warming, carbon capture and storage/utilization is the most promising as it provides opportunity for meeting the global energy demand while significantly reducing the CO₂ emissions into the atmosphere.

Post-combustion carbon capture is the most widely used for energy generation as it can be easily retrofitted into already existing power plants and the use of amines for capturing CO₂ is also a widely established and accepted technology (Leung et al., 2014; Rao et al., 2002; Sultan et al., 2021). The traditional approach for capturing CO₂ consists of the use of amines to contact the flue gas stream in a packed bed or spray column, and the absorbent regenerated in the stripper for recirculation for further CO₂ capture. This is the most widely used and well-studied method for removing CO₂ from large point sources such as power plants, cement industry, and other industrial emitters. However, this approach is embattled with various challenges such as flooding, foaming, entrainment and very high energy requirement for solvent regeneration which also translate into very high operating costs which have made the technology somewhat unattractive (Bottino et al., 2008). Furthermore, treating flue gas streams from large sources require maintaining the gas speed between 1-2 m/s to prevent flooding and foam formation in the absorber. This results in high absorbent volume and large structure requirements, which does not only translate into high operational costs but also leads to high absorber and desorber weights, limiting the opportunities

for application of this technology in other sectors such as marine and offshore platforms, where space is rather limited.

An alternative technology which has gained some attention and interest is the use of membrane contactors for CO₂ capture. Membrane contactors have been widely used in various industrial processes such as water and wastewater treatment, food processing, pharmaceutical processing among others (Nogalska et al., 2019). One feature of membrane contactors that makes it very attractive and more promising is the high contact surface area for capturing CO₂ from the flue gas stream, allowing for a drastic reduction in the absorber and desorber units, critical for commercialization. The membrane contactor provides a liquid-gas contact system for capturing CO₂ into the absorbent. A contactor that is non-dispersive in nature with microporous membrane operates by combining the benefits of selective absorption observed in membrane modularity, compactness of the units, elimination of a wash section, as well as a larger interfacial area for mass transfer of CO₂ (Bottino et al., 2008; Liu et al., 2019; Luis et al., 2012; Ramezani et al., 2022). Therefore, Hollow Fibre Membrane Contactors (HFMCs) presents several advantages over traditional packed columns such as high selectivity, low energy requirement, operational simplicity, ease of scaling-up with high flexibility, stability in a variety of process environments and much importantly, a reasonable price compared to traditional columns (Echevarria Huaman, 2015; Ramezani et al., 2022; Rivero et al., 2020; Y. Zhang et al., 2013).

Typically, membrane contactors can be made of ceramic, polymeric and bio-composite material and the membrane-absorbent compatibility, chemical and physical stability are essential for achieving desirable efficiency for the capture system (Nogalska et al., 2019). The major factor that must be considered is capacity of the membrane to overcome wetting, as the membrane pores should stay dry and open for contacting with the gas stream to ensure proper performance. Ceramic

membranes are reported to demonstrate higher chemical and thermal stability compared to polymeric membranes, however, because the material used in their fabrication are metal oxides, such as alumina and silica, the hydroxide groups situated at the surface of the membranes result in a high hydrophilicity of the material, making it very prone to wetting (Abdulhameed et al., 2017; Lin et al., 2015; Yu et al., 2015). Current studies have focused on the improvement of membrane hydrophobicity to overcome the wetting of the membrane surface. Studies have been performed on different polymeric membranes such as polypropylene (PP) nylon, polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF), polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) and the results from such studies indicate that these classes of membrane are hydrophobic in nature. Using a thermogravimetric (TGA), thermomechanical (TMA) and infrared spectroscopy (IR) analyses, it was determined that among these only PP and PTFE did not show any changes caused by ageing, with PTFE showing the best performance with higher efficiency due to its structure and stability (Porcheron et al., 2011; Yeon et al., 2007). Bio-composite, just as the name suggests, incorporates biomolecules on the surface of the membrane to increase the concentration of CO₂ on the membrane side allowing for an enhanced CO₂ absorption by the system. Current studies have focused on the types of molecules as well as the method for modifying the surface of the membranes (Yong et al., 2016; Y. T. Zhang et al., 2010). Among these types of materials, HFMCs made from PTFE can be said to be a well-suited and sufficiently advanced for membrane-based CO₂ capture.

The design of a membrane module is specified by the various membrane parameters such as membrane material, internal and outer diameter of the membrane, membrane thickness, length of the contactor, membrane pore diameter, effective membrane area, packing density, porosity and tortuosity of the membrane. These parameters do not only influence the absorption performance but also the separation efficiency achieved (Cui et al., 2014; Hafeez et al., 2021; Xu et al., 2019).

Studies conducted by Li et al, (2021) on the effect of porosity and pore size on the performance of PTFE HFMCs, show that an increase in membrane porosity and pore size in a non-wetting zone improves the CO₂ removal efficiency. Thus, a large pore size is beneficial to reducing the mass transfer resistance encountered at the membrane, however, this increases the risk of membrane wetting during the absorption process. Per the results from the study, increasing the pore size from 0.15 μm to 0.18 μm allowed for an increase in CO₂ removal efficiency, while for a further increase of the pore size from 0.18 μm to 0.27 μm, the CO₂ removal efficiency decreased, which could be as a result of the wetting of the pores (Li et al., 2021). Hence, it is expedient to ensure the various parameters for designing the modules are within optimum ranges. For cases where the liquid is at the lumen side, increasing the fiber inner diameter will increase the gas volume and enhance separation efficiency (Ibrahim et al., 2018; Mosadegh-Sedghi et al., 2014; Ramezani et al., 2022; Rivero et al., 2020).

This work therefore focuses the performance of PTFE HFMCs developed by Ionada for contacting MEA with a flue gas stream to capture CO₂.

2. Experimental Section

2.1. Materials & Methods

In Figure 1, the configuration of the units in the Ionada pilot plant testing system, located at Halliburton Labs in Houston, TX, USA, is depicted. The membrane contactor modules utilized in this system were equipped with hollow fiber membranes made of polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE). The gas phase of the experiments involved a mixture of carbon dioxide (CO₂) and nitrogen (N₂), with the N₂ serving as the carrier gas. The CO₂ gas was sourced from Air Gas, USA, while the N₂ gas was readily available through the workstation's fume hood. In the liquid phase, an aqueous solution of monoethanolamine (MEA) was utilized without undergoing any additional purification

steps. The preparation of all solutions involved the use of laboratory filtered water, and the experiments were conducted at standard laboratory temperature.

For the experimental procedures, a CO₂/N₂ gas mixture with predetermined CO₂ concentrations and controlled gas flow rates was introduced into the shell side of the hollow fiber membranes using a volumetric mass flow controller. Simultaneously, the absorbent solution, consisting of MEA, was supplied through the lumen side of the hollow fiber membranes in a counter-current flow arrangement using a peristaltic pump. Throughout the experiments, the feed MEA solution continuously circulated within the testing system.

Regarding the gas phase, key parameters such as CO₂ concentration, gas flow rate, pressure, as well as the relative humidity at the inlet and outlet of the gas mixture, were closely monitored. To ensure safety, the treated gas stream was directed to the fume hood to prevent the system from operating under pressurized conditions.

Regarding the liquid phase, important parameters including pH, flow rate, and temperature of both the influent and effluent aqueous solutions were monitored throughout the experimental runs.

Upon completion of the experiments, a thorough cleaning procedure was carried out to prepare the test system for subsequent experiments. This involved passing nitrogen (N₂) gas through the gas side of the system and circulating filtered water through the liquid side to eliminate any remaining impurities. By doing so, the test system was effectively purged and ready for the next set of experiments.

Each experiment was conducted for a sufficient duration to ensure that the system reached equilibrium conditions. The steady-state CO₂ concentrations in the outlet gas stream were measured and utilized for calculating the CO₂ flux and separation efficiency under the specific

experimental conditions. To provide a comprehensive overview, Table 1 summarizes the various operational conditions employed in this study.

The obtained results were subsequently compared with the simulation results obtained using identical operating conditions in the capture process. This comparison allowed for an evaluation of the experimental outcomes against the simulated predictions.

Figure 1: Process Flow Diagram of the Gas-Liquid Pilot System for CO₂ Separation.

Table 1: Operational Conditions for Carbon Capture Experiments. *

Operational Variables	Conditions
Gas flow rate (SLPM)	1.0 to 10.0
CO ₂ feed concentration* (vol%)	4 -12
Liquid flow rate (SLPM)	0.2 to 1.0
MEA concentration (wt%)	30

* *The CO₂ was balanced with nitrogen (N₂) to achieve the desired gas mixture.*

* *All solutions were prepared using distilled water, ensuring the absence of impurities.*

* *The experiments were conducted at a controlled temperature of 20±1 °C to maintain consistent and reproducible conditions.*

2.2. Modeling & Simulation

During the developmental phase of Ionada's membrane contactors, the absence of commercially available simulation software for predicting carbon capture processes using membrane contactors posed a challenge. Traditional mathematical solvers were found to be inefficient in simultaneously solving multiple material balances within the complex multi-stage membrane unit. To overcome this limitation, a membrane contactor process simulation developed by the Foundation for Scientific and Industrial Research (SINTEF) and a user-defined mass transfer correlation developed by Bryan Research and Engineering (BRE) LLC were employed in this study. This combination provided a user-friendly, efficient, and flexible model for simulating, evaluating, and optimizing the carbon capture process. In order to validate the accuracy of the simulation model, a comparative analysis was performed between the simulated results and the experimental data under specified operating conditions.

2.3. Supporting Theory for Model Development

2.3.1. CO₂ flux across the membranes

Two significant parameters useful for measuring the absorption performance of any given absorption system and the absorber used are the CO₂ absorption flux and the overall mass transfer coefficient. The overall mass transfer coefficient in CO₂ capture, also known as the total transfer velocity, accounts for the driving force required for transporting CO₂ from the gas phase to the liquid phase, and this can be expressed in terms of the gas phase or the liquid phase. When defined in terms of the gas phase, it is termed as the gas-phase overall mass transfer coefficient while it is termed as the liquid-phase mass transfer co-efficient when defined in terms of the liquid phase.

The resistance to mass transfer of the CO₂ is observed in the liquid phase, gas phase and the membrane. This collective resistance is termed the overall mass transfer resistance, which is expressed as the inverse of the overall mass transfer coefficient. Therefore, a lower mass transfer co-efficient suggests a high resistance to the transfer of CO₂ molecules into the absorbent. Thus, the overall mass transfer coefficient determines the rate of CO₂ transfer from the gas phase to the liquid phase (Ramezani et al., 2022; Rivero et al., 2020). Also crucial is the surface area available for contact between the gas phase and the liquid phase and its impact on CO₂ transfer, known as the CO₂ absorption flux. This is described by equations 1 and 2 and it defines the rate of flow of CO₂ per unit surface area normal to the direction of gas flow (Mansourizadeh et al., 2009; Qazi et al., 2020).

$$j_{CO_2} = \frac{Q_{g.in} \cdot C_{g.in} - Q_{g.out} \cdot C_{g.out}}{A} = K_{exp} \cdot \Delta C_g \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta C_g = \frac{C_{g.in} - C_{g.out}}{\ln\left(\frac{C_{g.in}}{C_{g.out}}\right)} \quad (2)$$

To effectively design and optimize the capture process, the CO₂ absorption flux as well as the mass transfer coefficient must be taken into consideration in order to specify and define the sizing and design of the HFMC, as these parameters, consequently, affect the capital cost of investment for the capture process. For instance, for a fixed capital investment, there is the need for a solvent and HFMC system with a high overall mass transfer coefficient and CO₂ absorption flux (Bein et al., 2021; Cui et al., 2014; Uragami, 2017).

In CO₂ capture using membrane contactors, the gas must first diffuse across the membrane wall before it comes into contact with the liquid solvent where it becomes chemically bonded to the solvent, as illustrated by Figure 2. As a consequence, the overall mass transfer coefficient in the gas-liquid absorption membrane contactor system is expressed as a function of the gas, membrane and liquid mass transfer coefficient provided in equation 3, and for a hydrophobic membrane where the pores of the membrane are gas-filled, and the mass transfer coefficient across the membrane is defined by equation 4.

$$\frac{1}{K_G} = \frac{1}{k_G} + \frac{RT}{k_M} + \frac{H}{k_L} \quad (3)$$

$$k_M = \frac{D_{G,M} \varepsilon}{\delta_\tau} \quad (4)$$

Figure 2: Film theory for mass transfer across a membrane interface (DeMontigny, 2004)

In the evaluation of the effective diffusion coefficient, the molecular and Knudsen diffusion processes were both taken into consideration while the porous solid model developed by Harriot (1975) was used in estimating the effective thermal conductivity of the membranes. These are expressed by equations 5 and 6 (Harriott, 1975; van den Berg et al., 1992). The physical liquid mass transfer coefficient for liquid flow in the lumen of the fibre was determined from the Graetz-Leveque correlation, provided by equation 7 (Yang et al., 1986).

$$\frac{1}{D_j^{eff}} = \frac{\tau}{\varepsilon} \left(\frac{1}{D_j} + \frac{1}{D_{kj}} \right) \quad (5)$$

$$\lambda_m^{eff} = \lambda_s \frac{1-\varepsilon}{\tau} \quad (6)$$

$$Sh_l = \frac{k_l d_m^{in}}{D_{j,l}} = 1.62 \left[\frac{a_m^{in}}{H} Re_l Sc_l \right]^{1/3} \quad (7)$$

For gas flow in the shell side of the module, the mass transfer coefficient described by the following correlation was used (Feron et al., 2002).

$$Sh_g = \frac{k_g d_m^{out}}{D_{j,g}} = 0.9 Re_g^{0.5} Sc_g^{0.33} \quad (8)$$

Also taken into consideration is the heat transfer co-efficient for the external flow. This was evaluated from the correlation developed by Sparrow et al. (2004) for convective heat transfer of air over a cylindrical configuration.

$$Nu_g = \frac{\alpha_g d_m^{out}}{\lambda_g} = 0.25 + \left[0.4 Re_g^{\frac{1}{2}} + 0.06 Re_g^{\frac{2}{3}} \right] Pr_g^{0.37} \left(\frac{\mu_g}{\mu_w} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}} \quad (9)$$

2.3.2. Mass Transfer Performance in Gas-Liquid Membrane Contacting

Figure 3 depicts the concentration profiles that form based on the resistance to mass transfer for transporting species "i" from the gas phase to the liquid phase through the microporous hydrophobic membrane. In gas-liquid membrane contacting systems, either the gas or liquid phase can be introduced through the lumen or shell-side of the hollow fiber membrane module. However, for lab scale studies, directing the gas phase through the lumen-side offers the advantage of minimizing potential maldistribution (Ghobadi, et al., 2018). The resistance to mass transfer in the case of a hydrophobic hollow fiber membrane configuration, with the gas phase in the lumen-side and the liquid phase in the shell-side, can be elucidated using a resistance-in-series model expressed by Equations (10) and (11) (Drioli, et al., 2006):

$$\frac{1}{K_l d_o} = \frac{1}{k_{ils} d_o} + \frac{1}{k_{im} H_{adi} d_{lm}} + \frac{1}{k_{igt} H_{adi} d_i} \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{1}{K_g d_o} = \frac{H_{adi}}{k_{ils} d_o} + \frac{1}{k_{im} d_{lm}} + \frac{1}{k_{igt} d_i} \quad (11)$$

In the given equations, K_g represents the overall mass transfer coefficient based on the gas phase, while K_l represents the overall mass transfer coefficient based on the liquid phase. The individual mass transfer coefficients for species "i" are denoted as k_{im} for the membrane, k_{ils} for the liquid

at the shell-side, and k_{igt} for the gas at the lumen-side. The adimensional Henry's constant is represented by H_{adi} . Additionally, d_i , d_o and d_{lm} correspond to the inner, outer, and logarithmic mean diameters of the hollow fibers, respectively.

The mass transfer coefficient on the lumen-side can be described using Leveque's widely recognized mass transfer correlation, expressed by Equation (12) (Ghobadi, et al., 2018):

$$Sh = \frac{k_g d}{D} = 1.62 \left(\frac{d^2 v}{LD} \right)^{1/3} \quad (12)$$

In Equation (12), Sh represents the Sherwood number, k_g is the individual mass transfer coefficient of the gas phase, d refers to the diameter of the hollow fiber, v represents the fluid velocity, L denotes the length of the fiber, and D represents the diffusion coefficient of species "i" into the fluid.

Unlike the lumen-side, the mass transfer transport on the shell-side is less well-defined, primarily due to stagnant zones, flow maldistribution, channelling phenomena, and frequent occurrences of stream splitting and remixing, particularly in comparison to the lumen-side . Wickramasinghe et al. (1992) proposed the following correlation in their study for Graetz number (Gz) values below 60, based on a closed packed fiber module, as shown in Equation (13):

$$Sh = \frac{k_l d}{D} = 0.019 Gz \quad (13)$$

In Equation (13), k_l represents the individual mass transfer coefficient of the liquid phase. The Graetz number (Gz) is defined by Equation (14) (Ghobadi, et. al., 2018):

$$Gz = \frac{v d^2}{DL} \quad (14)$$

Figure 3: Mass transfer regions and resistance-in-series model in hydrophobic gas-liquid membrane contactor system (Ghobadi et al, 2018).

2.3.3. Carbon Dioxide Reaction Mechanism with Aqueous Alkanolamines

The kinetics of the reaction between carbon dioxide and an aqueous solution of alkanolamines can be elucidated by a mechanism that involves the formation of a zwitterion (as shown in Equation (15)), followed by the proton removal by all bases present in the solution (as represented in Equation (16)) (Ghobadi, et. al., 2018):

In this mechanism, R_1 represents an alkyl group, and R_2 represents H for primary amines or an alkyl group for secondary amines. This reaction mechanism is applicable to conventional primary and secondary alkanolamines, including MEA, DEA, AHPD, and AMPD (Paul, et. al., 2007).

Based on the assumption of quasi-steady-state conditions for the zwitterion concentration, the overall reaction rate of carbon dioxide with primary and secondary alkanolamines can be described by Equation (17) (Paul, et. al., 2007):

$$r_{CO_2-RNH_2} = \frac{k_2[CO_2][RNH_2]}{1 + \frac{k_{-1}}{\sum k_b[base]}} \quad (17)$$

In Equation (17), $\sum k_b[base]$ represents the combined contribution of all available bases in the aqueous solution for the removal of protons.

For the reaction between carbon dioxide and tertiary alkanolamines (TEA), a second-order reaction rate can be employed, as shown in Equation (18) (Ghobadi, et. al., 2018):

$$r_{CO_2-Amine} = k_2[CO_2][Amine] \quad (18)$$

Table 2 provides the kinetic constants for the primary, secondary, and tertiary alkanolamines utilized in this study.

Table 2: Kinetics* of the CO₂ reaction with alkanolamines: monoethanolamine (MEA), diethanolamine (DEA), and triethanolamine (TEA) (Ghobadi, et al, 2018).

System	Temperature (K)	Alkanolamine Concentration (kmol.m ⁻³)	m	n	Reaction Rate Constant (kmol.m ⁻³) ⁻ⁿ .s ⁻¹
CO ₂ -MEA-H ₂ O	293	02-2.02	1	1	4300
	298	0.0265-0.0828	1	1	6000
	298	0.49-1.71	1	1	5868
CO ₂ -DEA-H ₂ O	293	0.250-0.820	1	2	840
	298	0.249-1.922	1	1	1340
	298	0.125-2.00	1	2	1270
CO ₂ -TEA-H ₂ O	298	0.1-1.0	1	1	2.7
	298	0.52-1.890	1	1	3.5

$$*r = k[CO_2]^m[MEA]^n$$

$$r = k[CO_2][DEA]^n$$

$$r = k[CO_2]^m[TEA]^n$$

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. Effect of liquid-to-gas (L/G) ratio on capture efficiency

The ratio of absorbent to exhaust gas introduced into the absorber, known as the liquid-to-gas (L/G) ratio, is a crucial parameter in process design for carbon capture. A higher liquid flow rate generally results in a higher capture efficiency. Studies conducted by Rajiman et al. (2020) demonstrated that using a packed bed column with 30 wt% MEA as the absorbent, an L/G ratio of 0.7 achieved approximately 15% higher CO₂ removal efficiency compared to an L/G ratio of 0.6. This improvement is attributed to the increased availability of amine molecules for CO₂ reaction, leading to enhanced absorption efficiency (Rajiman et al., 2020). Similar findings were reported by Pascu et al. (2016). However, the results also indicated that with higher L/G ratios, there is not only an increase in solvent requirement but also a corresponding rise in energy consumption for solvent regeneration. While a higher L/G ratio improves CO₂ absorption efficiency, it also escalates the overall energy consumption for solvent regeneration (Pascu et al., 2016). It is

important to note that increased energy consumption for solvent regeneration indirectly contributes to CO₂ emissions, which impacts the actual amount of CO₂ emissions avoided by the capture process. Hence, determining an optimal L/G ratio is crucial to ensure the overall process efficiency, considering both capture efficiency and energy requirements for solvent regeneration.

Figure 4 demonstrates the impact of increased gas flowrate while keeping the liquid flowrate constant on the capture efficiency. It reveals that as the gas flowrate increases, the capture efficiency decreases. This phenomenon can be attributed to two primary factors. Firstly, at higher gas flowrates, there is a limited number of amine molecules available for CO₂ reaction, resulting in reduced capture efficiency. Secondly, since the flue gas mixture primarily consists of 92% N₂, as the gas flowrate increases, the overall amount of available CO₂ decreases relative to the total gas flowrate passing through the membrane pores, significantly affecting CO₂ absorption efficiency. Furthermore, with higher gas flowrates, the residence time of the gas per unit area decreases, leading to a lower CO₂ capture efficiency. Consequently, a relatively lower gas flowrate is preferred; however, the optimal flowrate choice is dependent on the exhaust gas flowrate being treated. Therefore, it is crucial to identify the optimal liquid-to-gas flowrate ratio that ensures an effective capture process.

Figure 4: Gas flowrate versus CO₂ Capture Efficiency

Experimental runs were conducted at different liquid-to-gas ratios to investigate their impact on the CO₂ mass flux and the rate of CO₂ absorption. The results are summarized in Figures 5 and 6, which illustrate the relationship between the CO₂ mass flux and the rate of CO₂ absorption. It is evident that as the CO₂ flux increases, there is a corresponding increase in the rate of CO₂ absorption, and vice versa.

To validate the experimental data, the process was simulated using a specially developed model in ProMax. A parity plot comparing the CO₂ flux obtained from both approaches is presented in Figure 7. The absolute average deviation between the experimental and simulated results was found to be 4%, indicating a strong correlation between the two.

These findings validate the reliability of the experimental data and the accuracy of the simulation model, further supporting the effectiveness of the approach in capturing and analyzing the CO₂ absorption process.

Figure 5: CO₂ mass flux from different experimental runs

Figure 6: Rate of CO₂ absorption at varying experimental runs

Figure 7: Parity plot on CO₂ mass flux from experimental and simulation data

3.2. Effect of number of modules on capture efficiency

The modularized system for CO₂ capture offers the advantage of scalability, allowing for handling higher exhaust gas flowrates by increasing the number of units. To investigate the performance of the capture process with varying gas flowrates, a study was conducted based on the total number of modules utilized. The results, as depicted in Figure 8, clearly demonstrate the impact of the number of modules on the achieved CO₂ capture efficiency.

The findings reveal a consistent increase in capture efficiency as the number of modules is increased within the range examined during the experimental runs. This outcome is of great significance as it validates the practical application of membrane contactors in a modularized approach. It confirms that scaling up the number of units enables the attainment of the desired CO₂ removal efficiency for a given gas flowrate, without the need for a complete unit replacement and associated costs.

This observation underscores the versatility and cost-effectiveness of the modularized membrane contactor system in meeting the requirements of different exhaust gas flowrates, making it a promising technology for efficient CO₂ capture and removal.

Figure 8: Effect of number of modules on CO₂ capture efficiency

3.3. Simulation on traditional packed column and HFMC

After successfully validating the results obtained from the dedicated model for CO₂ capture using Ionada's Hollow Fiber Membrane Contactors (HFMC) technology experimentally, it was important to compare its performance with the well-established packed bed columns, which are widely used with 30 wt% MEA as the absorbent. In order to effectively compare Ionada's HFMC technology with the traditional packed bed columns, simulations were conducted for both technologies under identical conditions.

The analysis focused on two different gas flowrates: 1 TPD and 55 TPD. The target was to achieve a specific CO₂ capture efficiency at a designated liquid-to-gas (L/G) ratio for both cases. The

results obtained revealed significant advantages of Ionada's HFMC technology over the traditional packed bed columns.

Specifically, the HFMC technology demonstrated a remarkable 20% reduction in solvent regeneration energy requirements compared to the traditional packed bed column. This reduction in energy demand for solvent regeneration is of utmost importance as it directly contributes to the operational costs associated with amine-based CO₂ capture processes.

Furthermore, the HFMC technology showcased a substantial 28% decrease in MEA losses compared to the traditional packed bed column. Minimizing amine losses is crucial since they are not only expensive but also lead to increased operational costs and environmental concerns.

The aforementioned advantages of Ionada's HFMC technology, namely lower solvent regeneration energy requirements and reduced amine losses, address two major challenges encountered in amine-based CO₂ capture processes. These results highlight the potential for significant cost savings and improved sustainability, making HFMC technology a compelling alternative to traditional packed bed columns.

4. Conclusion

The utilization of PTFE hollow fiber membrane contactors has proven to be a highly efficient and effective technology for the removal of CO₂ in post-combustion capture processes. In comparison to traditional packed bed columns, membrane contactors offer the advantage of modularization, making them suitable for a wide range of industrial applications, especially in space-constrained industries.

The obtained results clearly demonstrate that increasing the number of membrane contactor modules leads to improved capture efficiency and enables the capture of CO₂ from higher gas flowrates. This scalability feature indicates that the technology can be effectively scaled up without the need to replace existing units, thereby achieving the desired capture efficiency targets.

Simulation studies conducted for both membrane contactors and packed bed columns reveal significant advantages of PTFE hollow fiber membrane contactors. Specifically, when compared to packed bed columns, membrane contactors exhibit a notable 20% reduction in energy requirements for solvent regeneration and a substantial 28% decrease in amine losses. These findings hold great significance as they directly impact the operating costs associated with CO₂ capture processes.

Furthermore, the experimental results obtained thus far provide strong evidence supporting the feasibility of employing Ionada's hollow fiber membrane contactors in post-combustion capture (PCC) applications. This is further corroborated by the observed average absolute deviation (AAD) of only 4% between the experimental and simulated results, indicating a high level of agreement and reliability.

In summary, the application of PTFE hollow fiber membrane contactors in CO₂ capture processes offers numerous advantages, including modularization, scalability, reduced energy requirements for solvent regeneration, and lower amine losses. These benefits address major challenges associated with traditional packed bed columns, making membrane contactors an attractive and promising solution for efficient and cost-effective CO₂ capture.

Nomenclature

A = gas-liquid contact area (m^2)

C_g = concentration of CO_2 (mol/m^3)

D_j^{eff} = Effective diffusivity of species j inside membrane, m^2/s

D_j = Molecular diffusivity coefficient of species j in gas or liquid phase (g, l), m^2/s

D_{kj} = Knudsen diffusion coefficient of species j , m^2/s

d_m^{in} = inner diameter of hollow fibre membrane, m

d_m^{out} = outer diameter of hollow fibre membrane, m

H = Membrane height, m

j_{CO_2} = CO_2 absorption flux ($mol/m^2.s$)

K_{exp} = experimental overall mass transfer based on the gas phase (m/s)

k_l = liquid- phase mass transfer coefficient, m/s

k_g = gas-phase mass transfer coefficient, m/s

Nu = Nusselt number

Pr = Prandtl number

Q_g = Gas side flow rate (m^3/s)

Re = Reynolds number

Sc = Schmidt number

Sh = Sherwood number

τ = Tortuosity factor

ε = Membrane porosity

λ_m^{eff} = Effective thermal conductivity of membrane, kJ/msK

λ_s = Conductivity of solid phase, kJ/msK

μ = dynamic viscosity of gas or liquid phase, $kg/m s$

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